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Birdcage Creative Economic Branding in Facing Business Competition Using SWOT Analysis: Study of Birdcage Craftsmen in Argosari Village, Sedayu, Bantul, Yogyakarta

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Abstract

This research aims to determine birdcage creative economic branding in facing business competition using SWOT Analysis, study of birdcage craftsman in Argosari Village, Sedayu, Bantul, Yogyakarta. This research uses SWOT analysis to find out what strategies are appropriate for Argosari Village bird craftsmen to overcome the problems they face. Development strategy using SWOT analysis is hoped that this can increase the added value of bird cage crafts in Argosari Village and can open up opportunities for the results of these bird cage crafts to be more widely known by the community so that it is hoped that they can support economic growth and improve the welfare of craftsmen and the surrounding community. The data source used is a primary data source, namely bird cage craftsmen in Argosari Village, which was taken using techniques of cluster random sampling, namely determining samples based on regional groups from members of the research population.

Keywords: Economic Creative, Branding, SWOT Analysis

1. Introduction

The birdcage industry is a form of creative economic business developing in Indonesia. By utilizing local potential, the birdcage craft business also hones the abilities and skills of the local community. Good management in this industry is expected to improve the community's economy. The creative economy is a part of the economic sector that uses ideas and knowledge with the concept of human creativity acting as the main production factor. In its development, the creative economy plays a role in advancing the country's economy by generating income, creating jobs, increasing export revenues, improving technology, increasing intellectual property, and other social roles. The creative economy also supports the creation of added value to domestic products and the development of innovative services that can support the country's economic growth.

Argosari Village, Sedayu, Bantul, Yogyakarta is one of the villages that contributes to the creativity of their residents by making birdcage crafts. The majority of residents in this village have a profession as bird cage makers,

although some are farmers. In Argosari, making bird cages has been passed down from generation to generation from parents and even ancestors. The production results are in the form of bird cages ranging from raw cages to ready-to-use cages. Birdcage products have characteristics that are different from bird cage craftsmen in other places. There are various types of bird cages and are supported by very good quality.

The problems faced by Argosari's craftsmen are increasingly fierce competition and efforts to expand existing markets. The craftsmen need the right strategy so that it can survive in facing competition in the business environment and maintain its market share. The main problem faced by birdcage craftsmen is related to marketing and capital. Lack of industry knowledge in business development where craftsmen do not yet know the opportunities, challenges, strengths, and weaknesses in the industry is also an obstacle to product marketing. Currently, the majority of craftsmen only sell their products in the surrounding area, where with the quality of the products they have, Argosari Village birdcage craft products can be sold to other areas and perhaps even penetrate the export market. This is quite hampering business development which will ultimately impact the welfare of craftsmen who depend on their income from these crafts.

This research uses SWOT analysis to find out what strategies are appropriate for Argosari Village bird craftsmen to overcome the problems they face. Development strategy using SWOT analysis is hoped that this can increase the added value of bird cage crafts in Argosari Village and can open up opportunities for the results of these bird cage crafts to be more widely known by the community so that it is hoped that they can support economic growth and improve the welfare of craftsmen and the surrounding community.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Creative Economy

The creative economy is a process of creation, production, and distribution of goods and services which in the process requires creativity and intellectual abilities (Siagian, et al., 2020). According to Rakib, Yunus, and Amin (2018), the main elements of industry in the creative economy are creativity, expertise, and talent which have the potential to improve welfare by offering intellectual creations.

According to Akhmad and Hidayat (2015), there are 14 sub-sectors of the creative economy, namely: (1) Advertising; (2) Architecture; (3) Art Goods Market; (4) Crafts; (5) Design; (6) Fashion (Fashion); (7) Video, Film, and Photography; (8) Interactive Games (Games); (9) Performing Arts (Showbiz); (10) Publishing and Printing; (11) Computer Services and Software (Software); (12) Television and Radio (Broadcasting); (13) Research and Development (R&D); and (14) Culinary. In its development, supporting resources, industry, financing, marketing, as well as technology and information are needed as pillars that will support the growth and development of the creative industry.

2.2. Development Strategy

Strategy is a basic pattern of planned current goals, shows the mobilization of resources, and shows the organization's interaction with the market, competitors, and other environmental factors (Boyd, Walker, and Larreche, 2000). According to Chandler (1962) Strategy is the determination of the long-term goals and objectives of a company as well as determining the direction of action and allocation of resources needed to achieve certain goals and targets (Craig and Grant, 2002). From this definition, it can be concluded that strategy is a way to achieve planned goals where it explains what will be achieved, what to focus on, and how to allocate resources and activities to face opportunities, challenges, and competitive advantages.

According to Fred R. David (2020), strategies can be grouped into four groups, namely:

1) **Integration Strategy**

This strategy requires companies to exercise more control over distributors, suppliers, and competitors, for example through mergers, acquisitions, or creating their own company.

2) **Intensive Strategy**

This strategy requires intensive efforts to improve the company's competitive position through existing products.

3) Diversification Strategy

This strategy is intended for new products. Diversification is an effort to search for and create new products or markets, or both, to pursue growth, increased sales, profitability, and flexibility (Tjiptono, 1997).

4) Defensive Strategy

This strategy intends for the company to take action to save it from greater losses. Companies with a survival strategy usually prioritize the stability of their target market.

Development can be interpreted as a process or effort to make changes either slowly or gradually by deepening and expanding knowledge through planning, implementation, and evaluation processes (Setyosari, 2012). Developing a business is the responsibility of every entrepreneur or entrepreneur which requires foresight, motivation, and creativity. If this can be done by every entrepreneur, then there is great hope for being able to turn small businesses into medium businesses and even into large businesses (Fadhillah, N, 2019).

Development of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) is an effort made by the government, business world, and society to empower Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises through providing facilities, guidance, mentoring, strengthening assistance to grow and improve the capabilities and competitiveness of MSMEs (Anggraeni, F.D, Hardjanto, I., and Hayat, A., 2013). Human resources are the most important thing in developing MSMEs. Therefore, society needs to be empowered to improve its quality so that it can improve the quality of the production produced. It is hoped that increasing the quality of production will encourage an increase in the economic welfare of the community concerned. According to Article 19 of Law no. 20 of 2008 concerning MSMEs, development in the field of human resources as intended in Article 16 paragraph (1) letter c is carried out by: a. promote and empower entrepreneurship; b. improve technical and managerial skills; and c. establish and develop educational and training institutions to provide education, training, counseling, motivation and business activity, and the creation of new entrepreneurs.

2.2. SWOT Analysis

SWOT analysis is an analysis used to determine the appropriate strategy to be implemented by a company based on public and market conditions, where opportunities and threats are used to identify the company's external environment and compare it with the strengths and weaknesses obtained through internal environmental analysis (Rusdiana, 2018).

In the internal scope, it is explained in detail the aspects that constitute Strengths (*Strengths*) and weaknesses (*Weaknesses*) by identifying several factors such as finance, and marketing. Products and operations, human resources, general management and organization (Umar, 2003), as well as research and development (David, 2004). Meanwhile, in the external scope, this analysis will explain in detail the Opportunity aspect (*Opportunity*) and Threat (*Threat*) businesses will face by identifying several factors such as economic, political, socio-cultural, and demographic (David, 2004), bargaining power of suppliers, threat of new entrants, and threat of substitute products (Umar, 2003).

SWOT analysis is carried out using the SWOT Matrix. The SWOT matrix can be used to clearly describe the external opportunities and threats facing a company, and adjust to its strengths and weaknesses. The SWOT Matrix (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats) is an important tool to help managers develop four types of strategies: namely SO (*Strengths-Opportunity*), and WT (*Weakness-Threat*). According to David (2004), the steps needed to compile a SWOT Matrix are 1. Determine the company's external opportunities, 2. Determine the company's external threats, 3. Determine the company's internal strengths, 4. Determine the company's internal weaknesses, 5. Match internal strengths with external opportunities and record the results in the SO strategy cell, 6. Match internal weaknesses with external opportunities and record the results in the WO strategy cell, 7. Match internal strengths with external threats and record the results in the ST strategy cell, 8. Match internal weaknesses with external threats and record the resultant WT strategy.

3. Research Methods

The type of research carried out is *field research* with a quantitative approach, namely conducting an in-depth study of the problems found in the field. The research was carried out through observations, interviews, document review, and questionnaires. The data source used is a primary data source, namely bird cage craftsmen in Argosari Village, which was taken using techniques of *cluster random sampling*, namely determining samples based on regional groups from members of the research population. Sampling was carried out by grouping craftsmen based on their hamlets, so samples would be taken from each hamlet based on existing data. The sample was taken randomly because the average answers from all sources were the same. The analysis technique is carried out using three activity flows that occur simultaneously, namely: data reduction, data presentation, and concluding/verification.

4. Results And Discussion

4.1. Internal and External Factors of Argosari Village Bird Cage Business

As a result of distributing questionnaires and interviews regarding internal and external factors to bird cage craftsmen in Argosari village, the following results were obtained:

a) Internal Factors

The internal factors in this research are related to the strengths and weaknesses faced by the bird cage business in Argosari Village. The factors studied include business management, production and operations, finance, product development, and human resources.

1) Strength

- i. Able to meet consumer demand
- ii. The infrastructure is quite adequate
- iii. Raw materials are of good quality
- iv. The products are of good quality, quite varied, and have distinctive characteristics.

2) Weakness

- i. Production output is limited
- ii. The financial situation is not yet stable enough
- iii. Capital is not enough for business
- iv. Craftsmen have never participated in training and business development

b) External Factors

External factors in this research are related to opportunities (*opportunity*) and threats (*threat*) faced by the birdcage business in Argosari Village. The factors studied include economic, social, technological, government, marketing, and industrial environment.

1) Opportunities

- i. Raw materials are easy to get
- ii. Buyer and distributor
- iii. Good cooperation between craftsmen
- iv. There is a community of craftsmen
- v. The marketing area is quite wide
- vi. Get entrepreneurship training from the Ministry of MSMEs
- vii. Developing his business through the world of Internet social media
- viii. Utilize financial institutions that are ready to help with capital

2) Threats

- i. Sales balance is difficult to achieve
- ii. Availability of raw materials depends on the season
- iii. Transportation costs are quite expensive
- iv. Not yet using promotional media
- v. There has been no special attention from the government
- vi. Production depends on the weather

- vii. Craftsmen do not yet have a good marketing network
- viii. There are still many customers who have not been served
- ix. Bargaining power is quite large
- x. Competitors' prices are lower

4.2. SWOT Diagram of Arogasari Village Bird Cage Craft Business

The SWOT diagram was created to further analyze the results of the SWOT matrix from the conditions of the internal and external business factors described previously. From the results of the matrix analysis, the position of the bird cage craft business will be known. The results of calculating the internal factor score (IFAS) are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: IFAS (Internal Factor Analysis Summary)

	Internal Strategy Factors (IFAS)	Weight	Rating	Score
Strength				
1	Able to meet consumer demand	0,142857	3,1	0,442857
2	The infrastructure is quite adequate	0,118541	2,6	0,308207
3	Raw materials are of good quality	0,147416	3,2	0,471733
4	The products are of good quality, quite varied, and have distinctive characteristics	0,12614	2,8	0,353191
	Sub Total	0,534954		1,575988
Weaknesses				
1	Production output is limited	0,115502	2,5	0,288754
2	The financial situation is not yet stable enough	0,113982	2,5	0,284954
3	Capital is not enough for business	0,110942	2,4	0,266261
4	Craftsmen have never participated in training and business development	0,12462	2,7	0,336474
	Sub Total	0,465046		1,176444
	Total	1,00		2,752432

The results of calculating the external factor score (EFAS) are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: EFAS (External Factor Analysis Summary)

	External Strategy Factors (EFAS)	Weight	Rating	Score
Opportunity				
1	Raw materials are easy to get	0,061259	2,9	0,177652
2	Buyer and distributor	0,061621	3,06	0,18856
3	Good cooperation between craftsmen	0,066246	3,1	0,205361
4	There is a community of craftsmen	0,063396	3	0,190189
5	The marketing area is quite wide	0,051287	2,4	0,123089
6	Get entrepreneurship training from the Ministry of MSMEs	0,05841	2,73	0,15946
7	Developing his business through the world of Internet social media	0,062684	3	0,188052
8	Utilize financial institutions that are ready to help with capital	0,055561	2,6	0,144458
	Sub Total	0,534954		1,305881
Threat				
1	Sales balance is difficult to achieve	0,056985	2,7	0,153861
2	Availability of raw materials depends on the season	0,057698	2,7	0,155784
3	Transportation costs are quite expensive	0,061259	2,9	0,177652
4	Not yet using promotional media	0,056985	2,7	0,153861

5	There has been no special attention from the government	0,055561	2,6	0,144458
6	Production depends on the weather	0,057698	2,7	0,155784
7	Craftsmen do not yet have a good marketing network	0,051287	2,4	0,123089
8	There are still many customers who have not been served	0,056985	2,7	0,153861
9	Bargaining power is quite large	0,060547	2,8	0,169532
10	Competitors' prices are lower	0,064109	3	0,192326
	Sub Total	0,579115		1,580207
	Total	1,00		2,768672

From the IFAS (Internal Factory Analysis Summary) table and the EFAS (External Factory Analysis Summary) table, the values for each factor can be obtained, including:

- 1) Strength factor: 1,576
- 2) Weakness factor: 1,176
- 3) Opportunity factor (opportunities): 1,306
- 4) Threat factor (threats): 1,580

Based on the calculation results above, the strength value is higher than the weakness value, namely (+) 0,399 and the opportunity value is lower than the threat value, namely (-) 0,178. So it can be seen in the following SWOT diagram:

Figure 1: SWOT diagram

The results of the SWOT diagram analysis show that the bird cage craft business in Argosari village is in quadrant 2 because the coordinates are in the Strengths and Threats area, which means it is suitable for using the S-T strategy.

The S-T strategy is a strategy derived from Strengths and Threats which is carried out by using the strengths possessed by the internal environment to avoid or reduce threats originating from the external environment. The strategies that can be taken in developing the creative economy of the bird cage craft business in Argosari Village are as follows:

- 1) Utilizing quality and easily obtainable raw materials as well as adequate infrastructure to achieve sales balance
- 2) Utilizing buyers who also act as distributors to reduce expensive transportation costs, so that product selling prices can be competitive
- 3) Implement the right pricing strategy by paying attention to raw material prices and transportation costs.

5. Conclusion

- a) From the results of the SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Treatment), namely:
 - a. The results of the SWOT analysis using the IFAS (Internal Strategic Factor Analysis Summary) table obtained a score of 2.752 and the EFAS (Internal Strategic Factor Analysis Summary) table obtained a score of 2.768.
- b) Based on the results using the SWOT diagram, it is found that the bird cage craft business is in quadrant II, where the strategy that can be used to increase the business is the ST strategy, namely utilizing the strengths it has to face the threats it faces.
- c) Strategies that can be taken in developing the creative economy of the bird cage craft business in Argosari Village using the S-T strategy include:
 - 1) Utilizing quality and easily obtainable raw materials as well as adequate infrastructure to achieve sales balance
 - 2) Utilizing buyers who also act as distributors to reduce expensive transportation costs, so that product selling prices can be competitive
 - 3) Implement the right pricing strategy by paying attention to raw material prices and transportation costs.

6. Suggestion

- a) Craftsmen must be able to maintain their advantages by maintaining product characteristics and good-quality raw materials
- b) Craftsmen take part in exhibitions that have been prepared by the government, namely those under the supervision of the industry department, to increase marketing and introduce their work.
- c) Craftsmen must prioritize quality and highlight uniqueness.
- d) Craftsmen and the government must coordinate with each other so that craftsmen can be supported by the government and receive guidance

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